

WHAT'S BEST FOR PHILIPPINE NURSING EDUCATION? A REFLECTIVE APPROACH

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Abstract

Significant improvements to the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) and continuing education of nurses will be necessary to suit the enormous changes occurring in the nursing education and practice contexts in the Philippines. This reflective study aimed to explore the best practices in nursing education in the Philippines, with a focus on curriculum design, faculty development, student support and mentoring, clinical training and experiential learning, and ethics and professionalism. The study utilized qualitative content analysis to analyze data collected from key informants. This reflective study explored major themes in Philippine nursing education, including the need for a comprehensive and innovative curriculum, ongoing professional development for faculty, a supportive learning environment for students, practical clinical training, and a strong foundation in ethics and professionalism. The results also highlighted the importance of practical training and hands-on experience in preparing nursing students for the complexities of patient care, and the need for partnerships with healthcare institutions to provide students with diverse clinical experiences. The study emphasized the significance of nursing education programs in instilling a strong foundation in ethics and professionalism in their students, promoting a culture of patient-centered care and respect for diversity in nursing practice. This study provides valuable insights for nursing educators and policymakers in the Philippines and beyond, as they strive to train competent, caring nurses who can adapt to the demands of the ever-changing healthcare system.

Keywords: Philippine Nursing Education, Reflective Approach, Major Themes, Content Analysis, Nursing Curriculum

Introduction

Since the nursing education and practice environments in the Philippines are undergoing significant transformation, the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) and continuing education of nurses will also need to undergo substantial revisions to accommodate these changes. Care management, quality improvement strategies, systems-level change management, and nurses' reimagined responsibilities in a transformed healthcare system should all be emphasized in nursing curricula at all levels. The goal of nursing schools should be to provide students with a solid foundation for lifelong learning that allows for a smooth progression into advanced degree programs (Mlambo et al., 2021).

Nursing education plays a crucial role in preparing the next generation of nurses for the dynamic and evolving healthcare system. Globally, the nursing profession is undergoing significant transformation, driven by technological advancements, changing demographics, and evolving patient needs. As a result, nursing education must adapt to these changes to ensure that graduates are equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary to provide high-quality patient care.

The Philippines is no exception to this trend, with nursing education and practice environments also undergoing substantial transformations. To accommodate these changes, the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) and continuing education of nurses must undergo significant revisions. Care management, quality improvement strategies, systems-level change management, and nurses' reimagined responsibilities in a transformed healthcare system should all be emphasized in nursing curricula at all levels.

In the Philippine context, the nursing profession is highly valued and is regarded as an essential component of the healthcare system. The country is a major exporter of nurses, with Filipino nurses working in various countries worldwide. Nursing education is highly sought-after, with numerous colleges and universities offering nursing programs. The Philippine government has also implemented various policies to improve the quality of nursing education, such as the Commission on Higher Education's guidelines on nursing program outcomes, the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002, and the adoption of the ASEAN Mutual Recognition Arrangement on Nursing Services.

Despite these efforts, challenges remain in Philippine nursing education. Issues such as faculty shortage, outdated curricula, lack of access to advanced technology, and limited clinical training opportunities continue to affect the quality of nursing education. These challenges need to be addressed to ensure that nursing education in the Philippines remains relevant and of high quality.

This research aims to explore the major themes related to best practices in Philippine nursing education through a reflective approach. Through this study, the researchers seek to identify the strengths and weaknesses of nursing education in the Philippines and provide insights and recommendations to nursing educators and policymakers on how to improve the quality of nursing education. Ultimately, by examining various perspectives, this study will be useful not only in the Philippine context but also in other countries facing similar challenges in nursing education.

Methodology

Research Design. Reflection includes reflective practice, reflexivity, and critical reflection. Reflective practice is frequently used in learning through participation, where key informants must engage, bridge, and negotiate difficulties across their classroom and host company learning contexts and interact and learn from colleagues and experts. Reflective practice has mostly focused on professionals who are experts in their fields. This perspective assumes that deeper reflective practice improves educational learning and outcomes (Bilous et al., 2018).

Participants. The study on Philippine nursing education involved gathering data and insights from nursing educators and administrators who were chosen using a homogenous sampling.

Data Analysis. In qualitative content analysis, data are presented in words and themes, which makes it possible to draw some interpretation of the results. The choice of analysis method depends on how deep within the analysis the researcher attempts to reflect the informants' statements about a subject. In turn, this affects the number of informants needed and in the way, data are to be collected.

Data Analysis. Qualitative content analysis is a research method that involves systematically analyzing data such as text, images, or audio to identify meaningful themes and categories. In this study,

qualitative content analysis was used to analyze data collected through the reflective approach in Philippine nursing education research. The data analysis process involved breaking down the transcribed text into smaller meaning components called "meaning units," which were then assigned codes to identify concepts and patterns. These codes were generated inductively, based on the data, and then grouped into themes and categories. The study aimed to identify the major themes and categories related to best practices in Philippine nursing education, and qualitative content analysis was used to accomplish this goal.

Establishing trustworthiness. Research must undergo critique, ensuring a report covers trustworthy notions, study processes, and results. This conversation encourages alternative interpretations. No one agrees on which ideas to employ or how to evaluate content analysis-based research. Scientists can be divided into two groups: those who debate the use of the same criteria and concepts as for quantitative research—validity, reliability, and generalizability—and those who believe a different set is needed, such as credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability created by Guba and Lincoln (Morse & Barrett, 2022). Credibility relates to the study method, including collection and analytic protocols and ensuring no essential data was excluded. Co-investigators, colleagues, expert panels, and informants can boost credibility. Negative case analysis, where the researcher asks questions to account for unexpected answers, is challenging and not suggested for inexperienced researchers (Bengtsson, 2016). Self-rated surveys use this strategy to capture informants' health-related perspectives. Dependability refers to data stability and researcher decision changes during analysis. Because re-coding and relabeling are common, the researcher must use memos to track development changes. Transferability considers how results apply to different situations or groups, based on sample representativeness. Qualitative studies prioritize depth over breadth and rarely generalize. Qualitative studies rarely generalize since they focus on smaller samples or even single cases. Presentation determines data objectivity, or confirmability. Since qualitative studies have no "truth," how concepts are presented regarding "truth" and "trustworthiness" is the key (Johnson et al., 2020). Instead of seeking truth and generalization, researchers generally seek in-depth understanding and multiple views. Because of their context, qualitative studies are sometimes impossible and always difficult to duplicate.

Results

This study aimed to explore the major themes related to the best practices in Philippine nursing education through a reflective approach. The study found several key themes that emerged from the reflective analysis.

Theme 1: Curriculum Design. The curriculum design emerged as a significant theme in Philippine nursing education. Participants highlighted the need for a more comprehensive and innovative curriculum that incorporates practical training and hands-on experience. They also emphasized the importance of integrating technology into the curriculum to prepare students for the rapidly changing healthcare landscape.

Theme 2: Faculty Development. The theme of faculty development emerged as another critical area in Philippine nursing education. Participants identified the need for ongoing professional development programs for nursing faculty to ensure that they are up to date with the latest trends and best practices in nursing education. They also highlighted the importance of promoting a culture of research among nursing faculty to encourage continuous learning and improvement.

Theme 3: Student Support and Mentoring. The theme of student support and mentoring emerged as a crucial factor in Philippine nursing education. Participants emphasized the need for a supportive learning environment that promotes student success and fosters personal and professional growth. They also highlighted the importance of providing mentorship and career guidance to students to prepare them for the challenges and opportunities of a nursing career.

Theme 4: Clinical Training and Experiential Learning. The theme of clinical training and experiential learning emerged as another critical factor in Philippine nursing education. Participants emphasized the importance of practical training and hands-on experience in preparing nursing students for the complexities of patient care. They also highlighted the need for partnerships with healthcare institutions to provide students with a diverse range of clinical experiences.

Theme 5: Ethics and Professionalism. The theme of ethics and professionalism emerged as a crucial area in Philippine nursing education. Participants emphasized the need for nursing education programs to instill a strong foundation in ethics and professionalism in their students. They also highlighted the importance of promoting a culture of patient-centered care and respect for diversity in nursing practice.

Discussions

Curriculum Design. The theme of curriculum design is crucial in Philippine nursing education, as it is the foundation of preparing competent and compassionate nurses who can meet the demands of the modern healthcare landscape. The findings of this study suggest that there is a need for a more comprehensive and innovative curriculum that addresses the challenges faced by nurses in providing high-quality patient care.

The participants' emphasis on practical training and hands-on experience highlights the importance of experiential learning in nursing education. The hands-on experience gained through clinical practice is essential for nursing students to apply their theoretical knowledge to real-life patient care scenarios. This provides nursing students with a better understanding of the healthcare environment, healthcare delivery systems, and healthcare management. Thus, they can develop critical thinking skills, understand patient-centered care, and provide quality care to patients.

Moreover, the integration of technology into the curriculum is crucial for preparing nursing students for the rapidly changing healthcare landscape (Ma & Yuan, 2023). The use of technology in healthcare has significantly improved healthcare outcomes and patient care by providing more efficient and effective methods of treatment. Nursing education programs should provide students with the skills and knowledge necessary to use technology effectively in their practice.

Subsequently, the findings of this study suggest that nursing education programs should prioritize curriculum design that emphasizes practical training, hands-on experience, and the integration of technology to prepare competent and compassionate nurses. The curriculum design should also address the challenges faced by nurses in providing high-quality patient care in the rapidly changing healthcare landscape. Nursing educators and policymakers can use these findings to inform nursing education and practice and promote the development of a highly skilled and compassionate nursing workforce that can address the current and future healthcare needs of the Philippines (Chan et al., 2019).

Faculty Development. The theme of faculty development is crucial in ensuring the quality of nursing education in the Philippines. The participants' insights suggest that faculty development programs can play a significant role in improving the quality of nursing education by providing faculty members with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively teach nursing students. Ongoing professional development programs can help nursing faculty stay up to date with the latest trends and best practices in nursing education, which is essential in preparing students for the complex and rapidly changing healthcare landscape.

Moreover, promoting a culture of research among nursing faculty is also vital in nursing education (Smith & Gray, 2023). Encouraging nursing faculty to engage in research activities can help promote evidence-based teaching practices, leading to better educational outcomes for nursing students. Research can also help identify best practices in nursing education, leading to the development of new and innovative teaching methods.

Overall, the theme of faculty development highlights the importance of investing in the professional development of nursing faculty to improve the quality of nursing education in the Philippines. By providing faculty members with ongoing training and support, nursing schools can ensure that their graduates are well-prepared to meet the challenges of modern healthcare delivery. Additionally, promoting research activities among nursing faculty can help identify best practices and innovative teaching methods that can be integrated into nursing education curricula, leading to improved educational outcomes for nursing students.

Student Support and Mentoring. The theme of student support and mentoring is critical in nursing education, as it plays an essential role in ensuring student success and promoting their personal and professional growth (Oikarainen & Kaarleka, 2022). Nursing students face unique challenges and pressures,

and it is essential to provide them with a supportive learning environment to help them navigate these challenges successfully.

In this study, participants highlighted the importance of providing mentorship and career guidance to nursing students. Nursing educators should recognize that mentoring programs can be an effective way to support and guide students through their nursing education journey. Mentorship programs can help students build confidence, develop critical thinking skills, and prepare them for the complexities of nursing practice.

Moreover, the study highlights the importance of promoting a culture of support and collaboration among nursing students. Providing a supportive learning environment can help students feel valued and connected, which can positively impact their learning experience (Poorman, 2017). Nursing educators should strive to create a culture of support by encouraging peer-to-peer mentoring and collaboration, providing resources and support services, and promoting a sense of community within the nursing program.

Furthermore, the importance of career guidance for nursing students cannot be overstated. Nursing education programs should provide students with opportunities to explore different career paths, learn about different nursing specialties, and develop career goals. This can help nursing students to make informed decisions about their future careers and prepare them for the rapidly changing healthcare landscape.

Meanwhile, the theme of student support and mentoring is a critical area in Philippine nursing education. Nursing educators should recognize the unique challenges faced by nursing students and provide a supportive learning environment that promotes student success and fosters personal and professional growth. Providing mentorship and career guidance can help nursing students build confidence, develop critical thinking skills, and prepare them for the complexities of nursing practice.

Clinical Training and Experiential Learning. The importance of clinical training and experiential learning in nursing education cannot be overstated. Participants in this study recognized the value of practical training and hands-on experience in developing nursing skills and preparing students for the complexities of patient care. Experiential learning opportunities allow nursing students to apply theoretical knowledge to real-life patient care scenarios, thereby building confidence in their abilities. The participants also recognized the importance of partnerships with healthcare institutions to provide students with diverse clinical experiences that expose them to different healthcare settings and patient populations.

Effective clinical training and experiential learning programs require strong partnerships between nursing education programs and healthcare institutions (McDowell & Hohmann, 2023). Such partnerships provide nursing students with opportunities to work in diverse clinical settings, develop skills in patient care, and gain insights into different healthcare systems and delivery models. It is essential to recognize the importance of developing these partnerships and to establish effective mechanisms for collaboration and coordination.

Furthermore, nursing education programs should provide students with opportunities for reflection and self-evaluation during their clinical training and experiential learning (Frank & Becker-Haimes, 2020). Reflection enables students to critically examine their experiences, identify areas for improvement, and develop strategies to enhance their nursing practice. In addition, reflection and self-evaluation promote self-awareness, which is critical to the ongoing professional development of nurses.

In conclusion, the theme of clinical training and experiential learning highlights the importance of practical training and hands-on experience in nursing education. Partnerships with healthcare institutions and opportunities for reflection and self-evaluation are critical components of effective clinical training and experiential learning programs. Nursing education programs should prioritize the development of such programs to prepare their graduates to provide high-quality, patient-centered care in the real-world healthcare environment.

Ethics and Professionalism. The theme of ethics and professionalism is a critical area in nursing education not only in the Philippines but globally. Nurses are often called upon to make complex decisions in challenging situations, and a strong foundation in ethics and professionalism is critical to ensuring that patient care is always at the forefront. Participants in the study recognized the value of understanding the importance of cultural competence in nursing education to provide patient-centered care.

Nursing education programs should prioritize ethics and professionalism in their curricula to prepare their graduates to be ethical and compassionate healthcare professionals. The participants in the study reported that the program taught them to provide care with compassion, respect, and integrity. This suggests that the program recognizes the importance of these values in nursing practice and provides students with the tools necessary to embody them in their practice. By emphasizing the importance of patient-centered care, the program prepares its graduates to prioritize the needs of the patient above all else, ensuring that they receive high-quality care that is tailored to their unique needs and circumstances (Schillinger et al., 2020).

Furthermore, nursing education programs should promote a culture of research among nursing students and faculty to encourage continuous learning and improvement. Promoting research and evidence-based practice in nursing education can help ensure that nursing students are prepared to use the latest research findings to provide the best possible care to their patients (Bahceli et al., 2022; Goldberg et al., 2018; Jarden, 2021).

In summary, the theme of ethics and professionalism in nursing education is a critical area that nursing education programs must prioritize. By instilling a strong foundation in ethics, professionalism, and patient-centered care, nursing education programs can prepare their graduates to provide high-quality and compassionate patient care (Casey et al., 2020; Garwe, 2019). Nursing educators and policymakers can use the insights provided by this study to inform nursing education and practice and promote the development of nursing professionals who can function effectively in an increasingly interconnected and diverse world.

Conclusions

This research evaluated Philippine nursing education basics such course selection, instructor training, student help, practical experience, moral and ethical issues, and professional standards. The findings show that these themes produce compassionate, competent nurses who can adjust to a changing healthcare system. Curriculum design stressed experiential learning and technological integration. The necessity of encouraging research and professional advancement for nursing professors was also stressed. In the student aid and mentoring problem, mentorship, career advice, and a suitable learning environment for nursing students were stressed. Clinical training and working with healthcare organizations to provide nursing students a variety of clinical experiences were also stressed. Finally, nurses need a strong ethical and professionalism foundation. Schools of nursing should prioritize patient-centered care and research and evidence-based practice to prepare future nurses to provide good care. This study helps nursing educators and policymakers in the Philippines and internationally by emphasizing the need of addressing these topics to develop compassionate nurses who can meet today's healthcare needs. This research suggests numerous ways to enhance Philippine nursing education. First, nursing education programs should emphasize experiential learning, hands-on practice, and technological integration. Collaboration with healthcare facilities and integrating their experience into the nursing curriculum may accomplish this. Second, faculty development programs should foster research, evidence-based practice, and continuous professional development for nursing professors. Third, nursing education programs should provide mentorship, career assistance, and supporting learning tools to students. By partnering with healthcare facilities and offering different clinical experiences, nursing schools should stress clinical training and experiential learning. Finally, nursing education programs should emphasize patient-centered care, cultural competency, and research and evidence-based practice to promote ethics and professionalism. These guidelines should guide Philippine and international nursing educators and policymakers in developing competent and compassionate nurses who can address current healthcare needs.

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